

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS MARKETING OF PRODUCTS IN ORGANIZED RETAIL SECTOR

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Abstract

Customer satisfaction is widely recognized as a key pressure in the formation of consumers' future purchase intentions. Satisfied customers are also likely to tell others of their favorable experiences and thus engage in positive word of mouth advertising. The present study aimed to study the demographic nature of the respondents in of Tamil Nadu state in India and to assess the factors of customer's satisfaction and their relationship with the selected demographic nature of the respondents. The data was collected by using questionnaire (Google form).The sample method used for the study was purposive sampling – 250 samples have been chosen using convenient sampling method. Customer satisfaction is a significant subject for most marketers. The result of this analysis suggested the degree of customer satisfaction in terms of services provided by organized retail outlets. . It is concluded that the significant difference in the mean of satisfaction is found only for the employee consciousness according to the gender of the respondents.

Keywords

Attitude, Behaviour, Customer Satisfaction, Retail Outlets and marketing of products.

1. Introduction

Retailing is one of the oldest businesses that human civilization has known. It acts as an interface between the producer and consumer, improves the flow of goods and services and raises the efficiency of distribution in an economy. For a strong, stable and consistently growing economy, a well-organized and efficient retail sector is a must. Most of the developed and even emerging economies had adopted the organized retail long ago and percentage share of organized retail in total retailing has increased over the years.

However, India, a land of self-sufficient villages, has continued to rely primarily on small, close to home shops. It is only off-late with pick-up in pace of urbanization and rising disposable incomes that the country started to take a few steps towards the organized retailing. A good progress has been made in the last few years, and the retail industry is off late being hailed as one of the sunrise sectors in the economy. Interestingly, for many years, retailers have been administering surveys to their customers to measure both their overall level of satisfaction and their opinion of various details of their store experience,

service and merchandise provided at organized retail outlets but they are not able to retain all their customers by providing solutions to them. Satisfying customers is one of the main objectives of every business. Businesses recognize that retaining the existing customers is more profitable than having to win the new ones to replace those lost. Management and marketing theorists underscore the importance of customer satisfaction for a business's success. Customer satisfaction is the key factor in knowing the success of any retail store or business; therefore it is very important to measure it and to find the factors that affect the customer satisfaction. Customers are most likely to appreciate the

goods and services they buy, provided if they are made to feel special. This occurs when they feel that the goods and services that they buy have been specially produced for them or for people like them. It should be always keep measuring in order to get feedback for the products and services in order to develop it further with wide customization. Customer satisfaction levels can be measured using survey techniques and questionnaires. Gaining high levels of customer satisfaction is very important to a business because satisfied customers are most likely to be loyal, place repeated orders and use a wide range of services offered by a business.

2. Overview of Indian Retail Industry

With a population of over one billion, India is one of the world's greatest rising marketplaces. In terms of purchasing power, it is one of the world's greatest economies. While retailing in India is still in its infancy, over a short period of time, some characteristics have emerged that are consistent with worldwide experiences. Organized retailing has grown in popularity in India's major cities, and the majority of metropolitan areas and other large cities are densely packed with sophisticated organized retail outlets. Numerous semi-rural communities have also benefited from

the establishment of such organized retail shops. India's retail industry is expected to reach US\$ 833 billion in 2013 and US\$ 1.3 trillion in 2018, growing at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 10%. Retailing as a whole accounts for about 10% of India's GDP and employs nearly 8% of the country's employable population. The organized sector accounts for less than 5%, indicating a massive market opportunity for the consumer-savvy organized retailer. The purchasing power of the urban Indian consumer is increasing, and branded merchandise in categories such as apparel, cosmetics, footwear,

watches, beverages, food, and even gold is gradually evolving into lifestyle items generally embraced by the urban Indian consumer. Organized retailing is experiencing a rush of new entrants. These companies are experimenting with a variety of different retail models. Numerous large corporate houses, including Aditya, Bharti,

Reliance, Pantaloon, Vishal, Tata, RPG, Raheja, and Piramals, have already entered this space with beauty and health stores, supermarkets, self-service music stores, new age book stores, everyday low price stores, computers and peripherals stores, office equipment stores, and home/building construction stores¹.

3. Review of related Literature

Samuel Augustina Lata Jayara and Priya (2017)² explored that the Indian retail is playing a very important role in recent era. Indian population consists of middle class income group of consumers who are more value oriented in seeking good quality of products with affordable prices, expect cordial environment for shopping, proper exchange and return of defective goods. This is one of the reasons to the migration of consumers from unorganized to organized retail sector. Thousands of retail store exist each of them compete with one another to meet the demanding needs of the customers

but is obvious to notice that people of modern era prefers to shop in Super markets, hyper markets, Department stores, retail chains and malls. This study is undertaken to study why the customers prefer to shop in the organized retail stores viz. Department Stores, Super Market, Corporate store, though chain of unorganized retail store exist. The researchers found that the irrespective of the socio economic status people do visit to the organized retail sector that provides variety of products under one roof. In order to collect the first-hand information the field survey technique was employed. Ashish Pandey, Avjeet Kaur (2018)³ examined that Retail marketing, as

¹ Berman, B. and Evans, J.R. (2003), Retail Management: A Strategic Approach, 9th Ed, Prentice Hall Publ

² Samuel Augustina Lata Jayaraj and Priya (2017) "Consumer satisfaction towards marketing of products in organized retail sector with special reference to Erode district International Journal of

Management and Development Studies Vol.6(10): pp.56-62

³ Ashish Pandey, Avjeet Kaur (2018) "A STUDY ON RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN RETAIL MARKETING, International Journal of Management and Applied Science, Volume-4, Issue-1, pp.58-60.

a critical component of retail commerce, has evolved significantly through time. Retailing in India and nearly everywhere else on the planet has seen a sea change in terms of retail marketing methods, industry size, retail formats, capital, and nature. When India gained independence, retailing was restricted to small unorganized stores. However, during the last six to seven decades, it has seen a dramatic transformation, giving rise to the organized retail sector, mall culture, and e-commerce. All of this has also altered and given modern retail marketing a completely new dimension. This in-depth analytical research paper will examine all of the current improvements and developments in the subject of retailing and retail marketing.

4. Importance of Retailing

In the marketing channel, the merchant serves as an intermediate since he is simultaneously a marketer and a consumer, and he sells to the last guy to consume. He is a marketing professional who keeps in touch with both the customer and the manufacturer, and he is a vital connecting link in the complicated marketing process. Despite the fact that manufacturers may sell directly to customers, this way of delivering items to end users is cumbersome, costly, and time consuming when compared to the task performed by a professional in the industry. As a result, producers typically rely on retailers to sell their products to final customers, a situation known as dependence. The shopkeeper who is able to give suitable facilities without increasing the costs of items by an excessive amount is rewarded by a greater or more devoted customer following.

5. Marketing of Products

Product marketing is a relatively recent notion in the marketing world. The process of introducing a new product to the market and guaranteeing its success is generally referred to as product marketing (or product development). Customer requirements analysis, product positioning and messaging development, as well as increasing demand and income generation for a product are all part of a company's product marketing strategy. Without the ability to contact the potential customers who will benefit from your goods, you have accomplished nothing. Product marketing include identifying the product's target customers and devising strategies for reaching them with the product⁴. Product marketing is critical in establishing the impression of a product among consumers and other internal teams, among other things. It helps these individuals see the importance of the product. Even after a product has been launched, marketing efforts must continue. Not only must it be introduced to the market, but it must also go farther in order to secure the product's continued development. It is necessary for the product marketing team to get client input in order to reposition a current product. One of the most important distinctions between product marketing and other forms of marketing, such as corporate or brand marketing or regional marketing, is that it is solely focused on a single product and functions as a consumer advocate. Product marketing may serve as a link between sales, marketing, product development, and customer service departments. Product marketers gather information from the other teams in order to better understand the needs of their consumers. Other teams rely on them for assistance in increasing their efficacy and efficiency⁵.

⁴ Dey, S. et al. (2012), "Organised Retail in the Rural Markets", IOSR Journal of Business and Management, Vol.6(1): pp.16-25

⁵ Goyal, B.B. and M aggarwal (2009), "Organized Retailing in India- An Empirical Study of Appropriate Formats and Expected Trends", Global Journal of Business Research, Vol.3(2),pp.77-83

6. Factors Contributing In Modern Indian Retail Marketing

The Indian retail sector has seen dramatic changes during the last few decades and remains very active. This continual and dynamic character of retail has also had a significant influence on the tools and tactics used in retail marketing. Today's modern retail industry necessitates the development of new and improved retail marketing methods. The different variables that retail marketers must consider in order to promote and sell their goods and services include the following:

1. Prioritize Organized Retail Marketing Over Irregular Retail Marketing: Due to the fast transformation of India's retail sector from unorganized to organized retailing, retail marketers in India must place a greater emphasis on tools and strategies that attract customers to and preference for organized retail formats.

2. Indian Youth Have a High Spending Capacity: India has the largest number of persons under the age of thirty-five, and their income levels have increased significantly. This is why retail marketers should priorities youth over the overall

Indian population, since youth represent the greatest opportunity for sales.

3. Consumer Thinking Shift: Over the last two decades, there has been a dramatic shift in the consumer mindset across all segments of society. Customers today are prepared to pay a reasonable amount for high-quality items; mall culture and the prevalence of organized retail formats have also demonstrated that customers favour more appealing, credible, and convenient retail forms over older, substandard retail formats. Retail marketers in India must grasp this shift in consumer attitude and adapt their marketing tools and methods accordingly.

4. Customer Credit Services: Various banks in India have made it simple to purchase products and services on credit. This is why customers today favour businesses who can give them simple loans or EMIs on products and services. A modern retail marketer must recognize this

and devise sales methods that allow clients to pay on credit.⁶

7. Retail Marketing Opportunities in India as a Result of Organized Retail

In the last two decades, the new notion of organized retail has radically redefined and reconstructed the meaning and character of retail in India. Foreign firms have poured into the Indian retail industry in droves over the last two decades, resulting in the emergence of several new retail formats such as malls, department stores, organized retail shops, convenience stores, and specialty stores⁷. All of these advancements and innovations in the Indian retail sector have also fundamentally altered the landscape of retail marketing. With the advent and popularity of organized retail establishments, malls, and the like, retail marketing methods and technologies have also evolved significantly, providing businesses with far greater options. Several current retail marketing techniques that provide retailers a plethora of options include the following:

1. **Utilization of Social Media for the Promotion of Goods and Services:** The present era is the era of social media, and this platform enables the promotion of goods and services at the lowest possible cost and with the greatest effectiveness. Modern retail marketers have been utilising this instrument to promote their goods and services on a large scale. Apart from social media, there are various additional online channels such as e-mailing that retail marketers utilise to attract consumers' attention and promote their products and services.

2. **Customer Follow-Up and Loyalty Programs:** Almost all modern retail marketers retain customers through the use of customer follow-up and loyalty programmes. Customer loyalty programmes, which offer discounts on subsequent purchases, have proven to be quite profitable for many businesses.
3. **Improved hospitality and customer service:** Modern merchants today give significantly greater hospitality to their consumers as a result of the introduction of quick retail management programmes and international working standards. This results in the development of long-term connections and trust.
4. **Continuous Employee Training:** Recognizing the critical nature of client retention and marketing, businesses today provide a variety of retail marketing training programmes to keep their personnel informed and efficient.
5. **Test Marketing for New Items:** Test marketing is a critical component of modern retail marketing since it enables retailers to conduct promotional activities on a very modest scale for new products and services in order to gauge early customer reaction⁸.

8. Statement of the Problem

Consumers perception towards the organized retail outlet differs from that of unorganized sector. The discussion held with the respondents reveals that they have suffered with various kinds of problems of 7P's of marketing mix, taking product the consumer expects more

⁶ Sikri, S. and Dipti Wadhwa (2012), "Growth and Challenges of Retail Industry in India: An Analysis", Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Management Review, Vol.1(1),pp.1-14

⁷ Dr. Dhillon, J.S. et al. (2012), "Emergence of Retailing Sector in India: Challenges and Opportunities", International Journal of

Management and Business Studies, Vol.2(4),pp. 41-45

⁸ Kanwaljet (2015), "Organized Retailing in India: Opportunities and Challenges", International Journal of Commerce, Business and Management, 4(2): 1117-1124

varieties of products of different reputed brands. Though organized retail stores exist, they rarely combine the proper blending of marketing mix in their sales strategy. As a result retailers are unable to fulfil the desired expectation of the products and services to the consumers

9. Research Objectives

The main aim of the study is

1. To study the demographic nature of the respondents
2. To assess the factors of customers satisfaction and their relationship with the selected demographic nature of the respondents

Research Methodology

Table 1: Demographic nature of the respondents

Demographic nature		N	Percent
Age	Young	86	34.4
	Middle	107	42.8
	Old	57	22.8
Gender	Male	133	53.2
	Female	117	46.8
Income	Low	91	36.4
	Middle	113	45.2
	High	46	18.4
Total		250	100.0

According the above said 3 variables, Table 1 depicts that 107 (42.8%) respondents are from the middle age (aged between 30 and 45 years), 86 (34.4%) respondents are young age (below 30 years) and 57 (22.8%) are from the old age group (aged more than 22.8%). 133 respondents are male and 117 respondents are female. The respondents are grouped based on their income, 113 (45.2%) respondents are from the middle income group (annual income between Rs. 3 lakhs and Rs. 10 lakhs), 91 (36.4%) respondents are from the low income group (less than Rs. 3 lakhs) and 46 (18.4%) respondents from the high income group (more than Rs. 10 lakhs).

The data was collected by using questionnaire (Google form).The sample method used for the study was purposive sampling – 250 samples have been chosen using convenient sampling method

Findings, Discussion and Conclusion

1. Demographic nature of the respondents

The study is analyzing the relationship between the nature of the customers and the factors affecting satisfaction. For which, the 3 demographic characteristics of the customers are considered, i.e., age, gender and income of the customers. The result is given below.

2. Factors affecting satisfaction and nature of the respondents

The main aim of the study is to measure the satisfaction of the customers towards the marketing of products in organized retail sector and the relationship between the nature of the customers and their satisfaction. The satisfaction of the customers is measured based on the factors called Product consciousness, Comfort with Entertainment Seekers, Extra Service Conscious, Store and Hygiene Consciousness, Price consciousness, Billing Flexibility & Facility, Sales People Consciousness, Confused by Over Choice of Store, Cash consciousness, Employee Consciousness and Taste consciousness. It

is analyzed by comparing the means of factors of satisfaction (ANOVA and Z test). The result is given below.

Table 2: Difference in factors of satisfaction according to the age

Factors	F	Sig.
Product consciousness	11.046	0.000*
Comfort with Entertainment Seekers	9.411	0.000*
Extra Service Conscious	10.102	0.000*
Store and Hygiene Consciousness	2.481	0.085
Price consciousness	4.717	0.009*
Billing Flexibility & Facility	2.929	0.054
Sales People Consciousness	8.926	0.000*
Confused by Over Choice of Store	12.017	0.000*
Cash consciousness	5.994	0.003*
Employee Consciousness	4.487	0.012**
Taste consciousness	2.903	0.056

* Significant at 1%; ** Significant at 5%

The Table 2 shows the difference in the means of the various factors of satisfaction according to the age group. The result of the ONE WAY ANOVA shows that satisfaction of the respondents towards the Product consciousness (11.046), Comfort with Entertainment Seekers (9.411), Extra Service Conscious (10.102),

and Price consciousness (4.717), Sales People Consciousness (8.926), Confused by Over Choice of Store (12.917), Cash consciousness (5.994) and Employee Consciousness (4.487) significantly differ according to the level of age of the customers.

Table 3: Difference in factors of satisfaction according to the gender

Factors	t	Sig.
Product consciousness	-1.891	0.059
Comfort with Entertainment Seekers	-1.483	0.138
Extra Service Conscious	-0.199	0.842
Store and Hygiene Consciousness	0.795	0.427
Price consciousness	0.953	0.341
Billing Flexibility & Facility	1.925	0.055
Sales People Consciousness	1.631	0.103
Confused by Over Choice of Store	0.950	0.342
Cash consciousness	1.198	0.231
Employee Consciousness	-2.028	0.043**
Taste consciousness	-1.232	0.218

** Significant at 5%

The above table indicates that no factor of satisfaction does not vary according to the gender of the respondents except the Employee Consciousness (-2.028 < -1.96). All other factors' values are

between the 1.96 and -1.96. It is concluded that the significant difference in the mean of satisfaction is found only for the employee consciousness according to the gender of the respondents.

Table 4: Difference in factors of satisfaction according to the age

Factors	F	Sig.
Product consciousness	3.749	0.024**
Comfort with Entertainment Seekers	17.258	0.000*
Extra Service Conscious	22.539	0.000*
Store and Hygiene Consciousness	5.573	0.004*
Price consciousness	2.056	0.129
Billing Flexibility & Facility	0.210	0.811
Sales People Consciousness	0.407	0.666
Confused by Over Choice of Store	5.239	0.006*
Cash consciousness	3.098	0.046**
Employee Consciousness	5.308	0.005*
Taste consciousness	4.351	0.013**

* Significant at 1%; ** Significant at 5%

The Table 4 reveals that satisfaction towards Product consciousness (3.749), Comfort with Entertainment Seekers (17.258), Extra Service Conscious (22.539), Store and Hygiene Consciousness (5.573), Confused by Over Choice of Store (5.239), Cash consciousness (3.098), Employee Consciousness (5.308) and Taste consciousness (4.351) significantly differ based on the income of the respondents.

10. Conclusion

The retail sector in India is undergoing fast transition, and this attractive and emerging market is seeing significant changes in terms of investment and development trends. Both new and established competitors in the sector are attempting to profit on novel retailing models. Around a decade ago, supermarkets and hypermarkets were extremely popular retail models; however, a tremendous transformation has occurred, with the majority of retailing being conducted electronically. The retail industry in India is developing fast and contributes significantly to the country's GDP, while also offering significant employment opportunities for Indian youth. It is concluded that the significant difference in the mean of satisfaction is found only for the employee consciousness according to the gender of the respondents.

The retail business is so profitable that more than ten retail corporations are included in the Fortune 500 list on a global scale. Though unorganized retail still dominates the Indian retail industry, organized retail is booming. This is also a truth that organized retail in India's immediate future is quite bright, and growth will continue in the next years.

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